

CAA Netherlands/Flanders – Annual Chapter Meeting 2019 Leuven, October 28–29th, 2019

LOCATION

The venue will take place in the Mgr. Sencie Instituut (MSI1) in Leuven. The workshop auditoriums are located on the 2nd floor: MSI1 02.15 and : MSI1 02.23.

Address:

Erasmusplein 2
3000 Leuven
Belgium

WORKSHOP PROGRAMME – OCTOBER 28TH

09:15 WELCOME @ MSI1 00.02

MORNING SESSIONS

09:30 – 13.00 Agent-based modelling with NetLogo: Are computer simulations useful for archaeologists? @MSI1 02.15 (by Dries Daems)

In this workshop you will receive a primer into agent-based modelling, looking at the potential and limitations of the approach for archaeological research. Following a short introduction, a hands-on tutorial will be provided to apply basic agent-based modelling practices with the NetLogo software. The workshop is aimed at beginners.

09:30 – 13.00 Spatial Databases: Combining the Strengths of GIS and Databases @MSI1 02.23 (by Devi Taelman)

This workshop will provide an introduction into the basics of spatial databases in archaeology. The topics that will be introduced are how to design and query a spatial database for archaeological research, and will introduce some advantages of using a spatial database. The workshop is aimed at beginners, but some basic knowledge on GIS and relations database concepts is useful.

13:00 – 14.30 LUNCH¹

¹ Lunch is not provided by the organisation. There are several options for lunch near the venue.

AFTERNOON SESSIONS

14:30 – 18.00 Archaeological Linked Data and Semantic Web @MSI1 02.15 (by Piraye Hacıgüzeller)

This workshop will provide an introduction to archaeological Linked Data and Semantic Web. The topics that will be introduced are: main Linked Data and Semantic Web standards and technologies, Linked Data production and curation, basics of semantic querying (SPARQL and triple stores), archaeological knowledge representation with Linked Data ontologies and vocabularies, and finally Linked Data applications in spatial humanities and archaeology. Hands on applications with Recogito, an open web-based semantic annotation tool for texts and images, will be included. This workshop is aimed at beginners who have no or little experience with the domain of archaeological Linked Data and Semantic Web.

14:30 – 18.00 Archaeological Spatial Data Visualisation using R @ MSI1 02.23 (by Danai Kafetzaki & Georgia Panagiotidou)

Introduction to spatial operations and visualisation possibilities of archaeological data in R. By the end of this workshop, you will have an overview of how to visualise raster and vector data using both static and interactive graphs. Previous experience in R programming is not required.